

A new *Acanthalophus* Morimoto, 2015 from China (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)

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Abstract. *Acanthalophus bicaudatus* n. sp. from Sichuan, China, is described, illustrated, and compared with the Japanese species thus far known, from all four of which it readily differs by the separate mucros of elytra.

Riassunto. Un nuovo *Acanthalophus* Morimoto, 2015 di Cina (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Acanthalophus bicaudatus* n. sp. del Sichuan, Cina, è descritto, illustrato, e comparato con le quattro specie giapponesi finora note dalle quali subito differisce per i mucroni apicali delle elitre separati invece che uniti.

摘要. 中国*Acanthalophus*属一新种(鞘翅目:象甲科)。本文描述并绘制了来自于中国四川的一个新种*Acanthalophus bicaudatus* n. sp., 通过与目前为止已知的日本的物种相比, 这四个物种可以通过鞘翅上面的锐突进行很好的区分。

Key words. Curculionidae, *Acanthalophus*, new species, China.

Introduction

The genus *Acanthalophus* Morimoto, 2015, belonging, according to ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* (2017), to the subfamily Entiminae Schoenherr, 1823 tribe Byrsopagini Lacordaire, 1863 was described to accommodate four unusually shaped montane species from Honshū, northern Japan (MORIMOTO, 2015). A couple of specimens belonging to a new species of this genus here described were discovered among unidentified material from China. This is the first finding of an *Acanthalophus* in continental Asia, and in a region quite far from the known distribution of the genus, suggesting its more widespread occurrence in the still poorly explored montane areas of China.

Material and methods

Labels of specimens are quoted verbatim, a slash separating different lines of the same label. The only two available females (one slightly immature) were not dissected to avoid damaging them. Measurements are taken as explained in BOROVEC *et al.* (2009), the total length of specimens not including rostrum. Terminology, particularly that of rostral regions, follows van den BERG (1972). Pictures of specimens were taken by Francesco Sacco with a Nikon D810 camera provided with an AF Micro Nikkor 60 mm 1:2.8, f/5.6 lens mounted on a bellow, lighted by a flash linked to the camera. Each specimen needed 170 shoots, then stacked with the program Helicon Focus to obtain good quality photos. The author ensures that the type material (including the holotype) will be made accessible for others to study.

Description of the new species

Acanthalophus bicaudatus n. sp. (Figs 1-2)

Diagnosis. Easy to distinguish from all the other four species of the genus by its elytral appendices obviously divaricate instead of almost united.

Figs 1-3. *Acanthalophus bicaudatus* n. sp., female holotype, 9.9 mm, in dorsal (1) and lateral (2) view. *Acanthalophus saitoi* Morimoto, 2015, female paratype from Yamagata: Tengendai, 6.4 mm, (3), picture from Morimoto (2015). Not to scale.

Type series. “China, W Sichuan, 15.6.2017 / 40 Km S of Hekouzhen (Yajiang) / Mts. W of Tanggancun vill. / N 29°41'31", E 101°01'08" / 3800 m, lgt. R. Schnal, M. Janata”, 1 ♀ holotype and 1 quite immature ♀ paratype (Enzo Colonnelli collection, Rome, Italy).

Holotype. Length: 9.9 mm. Pitchy-brown, rather shining, antennae, tibiae and tarsi dark ferrous-red. Dorsal vestiture of recumbent roundish to sub-polygonal golden scales, dense on base of rostrum and on head, moderately dense on pronotum, and less so on elytral intervals, the alternate ones of which bear a row of half-lifted whitish elongate scales widening at apex. Under side clothed with moderately dense golden oval scales, intermingled with lifted thin golden setae. Rostrum 1.40× as long as wide, barely curved in lateral view and slightly widening apically, coarsely punctured, thinly keeled, scaled almost to antennal insertion which is at apical $\frac{3}{4}$ of it, finely setose along its dorsal lateral margins, then glabrous up the smooth subtriangular epistome. Antennae rather thin, scape slightly curved at base and quite abruptly clubbed; first segment of funicle elongate and $\frac{1}{4}$ longer than the second which is slightly less than twice longer than the third, that is slightly longer than the following four ones, all longer than wide; club compact, elongate-fusiform, hardly longer than segments 5-7 united. Apex of head with two lateral sulci separating it from rostrum, interocular space flat, finely punctured and with a very thin median keel; eyes fairly large and slightly protruding from head convexity. Pronotum 0.85× as long as wide, moderately constricted at base and at apex, base almost straight, apical margin a little elevate above head and slightly convex, sides quite strongly curved. Disc convex, rugosely punctured, with two lateral depressions slightly basad of middle, dorsal sulcus very fine and shallow. Elytra (mucros comprised) 2.4 as long as wide, convex and with slightly flattened base near scutellum, maximum width at apical fourth, sides feebly curved, humeral calli wanting, each elytron with an appendix about as long as the first two metatarsomeres. Striae punctate. Interstriae wider than striae, the odd ones convex, particularly the third, fifth and seventh. Legs fairly elongate, femora quite

strongly clubbed and edentate, tibiae somewhat twisted, their internal margin slightly bisinuate, tarsi elongate, claws long, separate. Ventrites 1 and 2 rather convex and of the same length, placed at a level higher than the following three ones. See also Figs 1 and 2.

Paratype. Slightly immature and, except for the paler colour, almost identical to the holotype. Length: 10.8 mm.

Etymology. The Latin name of the specific epithet, meaning “with two tails” refers to the bifid apical appendix of elytra, an unique feature of this species.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is easy to distinguish from the others from Japan by the mucros at apices of its elytra separate by a distance at least equal to the diameter of the tip itself, giving the appearance of a bifid “tail”, whereas the four Japanese species, namely *A. matobai* Morimoto, 2015, *A. ozakii* Morimoto, 2015, *A. saitoi* Morimoto, 2015 and *A. shigematsui* Morimoto, 2015, all have the mucros of elytra appressed as to form a single “tail” (Figs 1-3).

Collecting circumstances. Unknown.

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References

- ALONSO-ZARAZAGA M.A., BARRIOS H., BOROVEC R., BOUCHARD P., CALDARA R., COLONNELLI E., GÜLTEKIN L., HLAVÁČ P., KOROTYAEV B., LYAL C.H.C., MACHADO A., MEREGALLI M., PIEROTTI H., REN L., SÁNCHEZ-RUIZ M., SFORZI A., SILFVERBERG H., SKUHROVEC J., TRÝZNA M., VELÁZQUEZ DE CASTRO A.J. & YUNAKOV N.N., 2017. Cooperative catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera Curculionoidea. *Monografías electrónicas de la Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa*, 8: 1-729.
- BERG H.C. (VAN DEN), 1972. The morphology of *Eremnus cerealis* Marshall. *Annale van die Universiteit van Stellenbosch*, (A) 47 (1): 1-58.
- BOROVEC R., COLONNELLI E. & OSELLA G., 2009. On the South African genus *Heisonyx* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Entiminae). *Acta entomologica Musei nationalis Pragae*, 49 (2): 841-850.
- MORIMOTO K., 2015. Tribe Tropiphorini (pp. 557-575). In: MORIMOTO K., NAKAMURA T. & KANNÔ K. The Insects of Japan. Vol. 4. Curculionidae: Entiminae (Part 2) (Coleoptera). *Touka Shobo Co., Ltd.*, Fukuoka, 758 pp.

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